

Annual Report for May 1, 2024-April 30, 2025

RCD Nexus

NSF CI CoE: Demo Pilot: Advancing Research Computing and Data: Strategic Tools, Practices, and Professional Development

[NSF Grant OAC-2100003](#)

May 1, 2024-April 30, 2025

For Public Distribution

RCD Nexus Team

Dana Brunson (Internet2)	Overall program leadership and guidance
Patrick Schmitz (Semper Cogito)	Enhancing/supporting the CaRCC Capabilities Model, portal development oversight
Claire Mizumoto (Retired, UC San Diego)	Professional development of staff
Scott Yockel (Harvard)	RCD professionalization (job families, staffing survey)
Thomas Cheatham (U of Utah)	Involving students in RCD/workforce development
Daphne McCanse (CaRCC)	Communications coordination and facilitation
Timothy Middelkoop (Internet2)	Professional development of staff

About the RCD Nexus

The RCD Nexus is funded by NSF's Office of Advanced Cyberinfrastructure as an NSF Cyberinfrastructure Center of Excellence (CI CoE) demo pilot. It is a Research Computing and Data (RCD) Resource and Career Center that creates tools, practices, and professional development resources to support individuals and institutions. RCD Nexus both leverages and augments the infrastructure of the Campus Research Computing Consortium (CaRCC) in order to reach, support, and engage with Research Computing and Data and other related professionals. CaRCC is uniquely positioned to support and grow the RCD community, with a vision to advance the frontiers of research by improving the effectiveness of RCD professionals and organizations. The CaRCC community is growing rapidly, with People Network membership increasing by more than 150% per year; the total count recently surpassed 2,000. Activities are expanding, including multiple new working- and interest- groups, as well as increasing partnerships with other RCD partners.

CaRCC's People Network and groups help RCD Nexus reach its intended audience, and the RCD Nexus has, in turn, helped the People Network and CaRCC expand rapidly, both in numbers and scope. With CaRCC's rapid growth, it has become increasingly difficult for it to be managed and overseen by volunteers alone. RCD Nexus has thus filled a critical role by providing central staff and resources to ensure organization, consistency, and professionalism as CaRCC progresses toward becoming a more formal professional society. RCD Nexus-funded staff largely led the general administration, management, communications, and engagement efforts – which allows CaRCC volunteers and members to focus on sharing their RCD-related knowledge.

The main areas of emphasis for the RCD Nexus include:

- A more robust and sustainable implementation of the CaRCC Capabilities Model and a new Community Dataset portal
- Conducting an RCD Workforce Survey and sharing the results
- Advancing the adoption of the Human Resources (HR) Job Family Framework
- Developing a Career Arcs resource for RCD professionals
- Curating leading practices for staff professional development, and for involving students in RCD workforce development

For information about the RCD Nexus, please visit the project website: <http://rcd-nexus.org> (which now redirects to the CaRCC Products and Resources page: https://carcc.org/products_resources/).

About This Report

This report represents the project year of NSF grant OAC-210003 from May 1, 2024 to April 30, 2025.

Any opinions, findings, and conclusions or recommendations expressed in this material are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the views of the National Science Foundation.

This work is made available under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 Unported License. Please visit the following URL for details:
<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

Please cite this report as:

Brunson, Dana; Schmitz, Patrick; McCanse, Daphne; Cheatham, Thomas; and Yockel, Scott. (2025) RCD Nexus Annual Report for Project Year 4. August 2025.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16989318>

For updates to this report and other reports from the RCD Nexus, please visit
<http://rcd-nexus.org>.

Executive Summary

The RCD Nexus project continued to both leverage and augment the Campus Research Computing Consortium (CaRCC) in order to reach, support, and engage with Research Computing and Data (RCD) professionals. These central services and support remain essential to CaRCC's success during this period of continued organizational growth. RCD Nexus currently fills this role by providing central staff, leadership, and resources as CaRCC works towards a long-term sustainability plan. Highlights for the reporting period fall into the following categories:

Communications and Engagement – We completed several successful events, including the third RCD Nexus Day co-located with PEARC24, which was attended by 121 people including 33 first time attendees; travel support was provided for 12 attendees. We continued the “Monthly Welcome” series to greet new community members, launched a popular series of research computing and data (RCD) program institutional profiles, and continued the monthly newsletter which consistently shows a high open and click rate averaging 45% and 10% respectively.

Developing Career Arcs – We continued our work to investigate the factors that influence RCD professionals in the course of their careers, analyzing the results of 14 in-depth interviews with a range of RCD professionals, and wrote up the results as a white paper. We also developed a visualization of the common paths to help RCD professionals in their own career planning, and to help hiring managers better understand where recruitment efforts can be effective. This was accepted at a poster presentation for PEARC25. Having completed the goals of their charter, the Career Arcs working group is now winding up activity, and will either transition to an Interest Group or be subsumed under the RCD Professionalization Working Group to carry on informal discussion and support others who wish to pursue associated activity.

CaRCC Capabilities Model – We completed several updates to the Capabilities Model assessment tool and data portal, including an Essentials version that focuses on 38 capabilities for new and emerging RCD programs, and a Chart-You-Own-Journey version that allows institutions to select specific capabilities to assess (e.g., when completing a follow-up assessment). We updated the benchmarking functionality to support benchmarking of Essentials assessments compared to the broader community’s responses to just those capabilities. We expanded the functionality of the data exploration tools to allow graphing and benchmarking down to the level of individual capabilities. We continued our monthly Office Hours series and initiated a Community of Practice to facilitate more discussion of practices among the many users of the Capabilities Model.

RCD Staff Resources –The Staff Workforce Development workstream held a workshop attended by 56 people with the topic of “What We’re Facing as Research Computing and Data (RCD) Professionals” as part of the RCD Nexus Day at PEARC24. The materials generated from the workshop were further refined and developed by the CaRCC Staff and Student Workforce Development Interest Group resulting in a paper describing a curated catalog of resources that can be used for training RCD Professionals titled “A Collaborative Catalog for Research Computing and Data Professional Development” that was submitted (and subsequently accepted) to PEARC25.

Student Workforce Development – The RCD Student Workforce continued to grow during the reporting period to a total of 78 members who meet approximately bi-monthly. This year the bi-monthly calls focused on establishing and building RCD student programs and how to train, manage, and mentor students within the program.

Job Family Matrix Adoption – Interest in the HR Job Family Matrix remains high. To date there have been 470 total downloads from 381 unique emails across 200 different institutions, including 95 downloads from the past year.

RCD Workforce Survey – In continuation of work in the prior year, the CaRCC RCD Professionalization working group completed additional analysis of the 2021 RCD Workforce Survey data (published in this [blog post](#)) and completed an updated iteration of the RCD Workforce Survey. The 2025 survey has been designed to preserve some longitudinal research value for aspects including respondent compensation, job titling, and education background, while also adding new content for aspects such as self-reported neurodivergence and reasons for employment changes. The complete survey was under IRB review as of the close of the RCD Nexus grant, and with multiple sponsors of gift cards to incentivize participation. As of the writing of this report, the survey was deployed in late July during the PEARC25 conference, as planned, and has been open for several weeks, already reaching hundreds of contributing RCD professionals ahead of a survey close planned for the end of August.

Program Administration – In addition to the project and budget management tasks associated with the grant, we coordinated the October 2024 CaRCC Annual leadership retreat and produced a [related report](#). We planned and executed the third annual RCD Nexus Day co-located with PEARC24, which also [yielded a report](#). We have planned and are preparing for the fourth annual RCD Nexus Day to be co-located with PEARC25. We led CaRCC Chairs Monthly meetings and the Logistics and Engagement Operations groups meetings. We coordinated a redesign and relaunch of the CaRCC website. We also ramped up continuing efforts to explore potential membership and financial models to support long term CaRCC sustainability, and facilitated the establishment of a Transitional Board to identify the best path forward.

Looking Forward – RCD Nexus support has provided critical infrastructure and central support for the growing CaRCC organization and serves to amplify the impact of CaRCC volunteers. However, the current level of support falls short of overall needs, hampering progress on important priorities. Looking forward, in addition to a number of specific priorities related to refining and developing additional tools for the RCD community, we are dedicating significant effort towards developing a long-term financial model to ensure CaRCC’s sustainability. This is among the main priorities for the CaRCC Transitional Board, with the others being the development of bylaws and other necessary materials to establish CaRCC as a not-for-profit organization (either independently or in coordination with a fiscal sponsor).

Table of Contents

1 Communications and Engagement	1
2 Developing Career Arcs	4
3 CaRCC Capabilities Model	5
4 RCD Staff Resources	8
5 Student Workforce Development	10
6 Job Family Matrix Adoption	11
7 RCD Workforce Survey	12
8 Program Administration	12
9 Looking Forward	14
10 Publications and Presentations	15
11 CaRCC Transitional Board	19
12 Committees and Working Groups	20

1 Communications and Engagement

Accomplishments for the reporting period in the areas of communications and engagement include:

- Hosting and promoting a series of webinars on “Requesting Resources via the National AI Research Resource Pilot” which were seen by more than 800 community members.
- Maintaining an active LinkedIn and Facebook presence to communicate with a broader audience about RCD Nexus and CaRCC tools and activities (Ongoing.)
- Completing communications and outreach efforts at several events including PEARC24, and SC24.
- Developing new print materials and event signage (Ongoing)
- Designing and launching a new website template for CaRCC and RCD Nexus, and then merging the RCD Nexus content into the CaRCC site to simplify community access to and discovery of products and resources.

Engagement efforts and events

During the reporting period, the CaRCC Engagement working group completed work on several efforts. The group enables the continued rapid growth of the People Network through leadership, membership drives, and identifying opportunities for in-person outreach through events.

Some specific efforts during the period include:

- Continued the “Monthly Welcome” series to greet new members of the People Network, answer their questions, and ensure they know about and get integrated into CaRCC groups and activities relevant to their specific needs and interests.
- Supported the CaRCC Parade Event in January 2025, providing an update for the existing CaRCC community and providing information on CaRCC groups and activities for new members.
- Completed the second annual “Bring Your Colleague to CaRCC” recruitment effort in January 2025 that encouraged existing members to invite their colleagues to join the People Network and/or attend working or interest group calls.
- Hosted CaRCC/RCD Nexus booth (in partnership with Internet2) at the PEARC24 Conference to inform attendees about CaRCC and RCD Nexus resources.
- Held a well-attended “Coffee with CaRCC” event at the Supercomputing Conference. Current members of CaRCC and those interested in getting involved with CaRCC met for a casual networking and informational event at the Internet2 booth.

Blog posts and RCD Program Stories - RCD Nexus produced the following blog posts and RCD Program Stories, in addition to monthly posts announcing People Network and related sessions.

- Apr 29, 2025: [Research Computing and Data \(RCD\) Monthly — May 2025](#)
- Apr 28, 2025: [All Things AI: May 2025](#)
- Apr 28, 2025: [Island Innovation: How the University of Hawaii’s Research IT Team Spans Oceans and Disciplines](#)
- Apr 25, 2025: [Make the Most of the NAIRR Pilot With a New Video, Report, and Meeting Materials](#)
- Apr 1, 2025: [Research Computing and Data \(RCD\) Monthly –April 2025](#)
- Mar 31, 2025: [All Things AI: April 2025](#)
- Mar 31, 2025: [Small Team, Big Impact: UC Merced’s Research Computing Journey](#)
- Mar 31, 2025: [Register Now for RCD Nexus Day at PEARC25!](#)
- Mar 4, 2025: [Research Computing and Data \(RCD\) Monthly – March 2025](#)
- Mar 3, 2025: [Meet the CaRCC Transitional Board Members](#)
- Mar 3, 2025: [All Things AI March 2025](#)
- Mar 3, 2025: [RCD Program Story: Cornell University](#)
- Jan 30, 2025: [All Things AI February 2025](#)
- Jan 30, 2025: [RCD Program Story: Northwestern University](#)
- Jan 8, 2025: [All Things AI, January 2025](#)
- Dec 13, 2024: [Exploring the Role of Research Computing and Data \(RCD\) Professionals](#)
- Dec 9, 2024: [Complementing a CaRCC Capabilities Model assessment with input from Researchers](#)
- Dec 4, 2024: [All things AI December 2024](#)
- Nov 26, 2024: [RCD Program Story: University of Oklahoma](#)
- Nov 26, 2024: [Submit your 2024 RCD Capabilities Model Data by December 31](#)
- Oct 31, 2024: [All Things AI November 2024](#)
- Oct 30, 2024: [RCD Program Story: Arizona State University](#)
- Oct 6, 2024: [All Things AI October 2024](#)
- Oct 6, 2024: [RCD Nexus Day 2024: Read the report!](#)
- Sep 17, 2024: [New Release: RCD-Nexus Portal \(CaRCC Capabilities Model Assessment tool and Data Viewer\)](#)
- Sep 11, 2024: [CaRCC/Internet2 to provide support for National AI Research Resource \(NAIRR\) Pilot communications and community Building](#)
- Jul 9, 2024: [CaRCC at PEARC24: Headed to Providence? Here’s your guide to all things CaRCC!](#)
- Jul 17, 2024: [Workforce Development: Maximizing Your Conference Experience](#)
- May 9, 2024: [CaRCC Capabilities Model Workshop at PEARC24](#)
- May 9, 2024: [NSF announces National Artificial Intelligence Research Resource \(NAIRR\) pilot resources now available](#)

RCD professional events

RCD Nexus held several successful events during the reporting period, bringing the community together to network and discuss common issues and challenges. CaRCC/RCD Nexus events help to forge professional relationships within the RCD community, and also serve to share and improve the products and tools produced by the RCD Nexus project.

2024 CaRCC Annual Retreat – This meeting brings together CaRCC chairs of working, interest, and operations groups as well as the People Network co-chairs and track coordinators, the CaRCC and RCD Nexus Advisory committees, and others from the broader community. Attendees represented a diverse range of institutions including research universities, liberal arts colleges, regional networks, and national organizations. The three-day event included two days focused on CaRCC strategy and planning, followed by a joint session with the Coalition for Academic Scientific Computation (CASC). The meeting [yielded a report](#), and led to the [resolution to develop an incorporation plan](#).

2024 RCD Nexus Day – RCD Nexus Day 2024 brought together 110 research computing and data (RCD) professionals from institutions across the U.S. including 62 first time attendees. The event took place on July 21, 2024, and was an official co-located event of the PEARC'24 conference in Providence, Rhode Island. Twelve attendees received travel support, which allowed them to attend both RCD Nexus Day and the full PEARC24 conference. In addition to a combined opening session and an evening networking session, the event included two concurrent workshops. Workshop 1 was titled *What We're Facing as RCD Professionals* and Workshop 2 focused on *Working with Secure Data*. The [2024 RCD Nexus Day Final Report](#) provides details and recommendations identified at the workshops.

CaRCC Town Hall at PEARC24 – This event brought together more than 100 members of the broader CaRCC/RCD community to learn about current CaRCC projects and initiatives, followed by an open discussion during which community members provided feedback and shared ideas to inform future CaRCC activities.

New working and interest groups

During the reporting period, two new working groups and two new interest groups were formed:

- The AI/ML (Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning) Facilitation Materials working group aims to develop resources and training materials to help RCD (Research Computing and Data) professionals effectively facilitate the use of AI/ML technologies. These materials, designed primarily for RCD professionals, will also help them work effectively with researchers and educators.
- The Anaconda Transition Working Group was formed to help RCD groups meet compliance with new license terms for Anaconda, a distribution of the Python and R

programming languages for scientific computing. They plan to do this in at least two ways – first, we plan to communicate with Anaconda to clarify its stance for organizations that do not fall clearly within the classifications outlined by Anaconda (such as national labs and teaching applications). Second, to provide information and guidance to the RCD community at large.

- The AI Facilitation Materials Working Group was formed to develop a set of resources and training materials for researcher and educator facing RCD professionals to effectively facilitate the use of AI/ML and AI/ML resources. The materials will be designed for RCD professionals in mind but will also include resources that can be used when working with researchers and educators.
- The AI Facilitation Interest Group was formed to develop and provide a community of practice for researcher and educator RCD professionals to effectively facilitate the use of artificial intelligence and machine learning software made possible by AI focused computational resource platforms and cyberinfrastructure. This community of practice is fostered via regular engagement with group members and relevant partners within CaRCC.
- The Research Cybersecurity Interest Group (RCsIG) will discuss and develop ideas, activities, and recommended practices for action at the intersection of Research Computing and Data (RCD) Facilitation and Research Cybersecurity, with emphasis on blending populations of RCD professionals and cybersecurity professionals working in research environments.

2 Developing Career Arcs

RCD Nexus developed a model of Career Arcs for RCD Professionals to explain career options and help existing RCD professionals pursue professional development and advancement.

Our key objectives were to address the following set of challenges, as identified in a series of workshops and meetings:

- Managers need better resources and the ability to offer defined career paths, so their staff are not forced to seek growth opportunities outside the RCD profession.
- Many RCD professionals say they see no clear path for career advancement; this is especially so for data-centric and researcher-facing roles.
- There is a national shortage of RCD (CI) personnel and high employee turnover, with significant training needed to orient new employees.
- There is no formal talent pipeline seeking to join the RCD field. Students who are studying in relevant programs do not have an easy way to learn about or enter the field.
- RCD personnel experience precarious employment with few opportunities for advancement.

We completed work to develop a framework for describing the roles and career arcs of RCD professionals and distributed content through community engagement. Specific activities included:

- Analyzing coded interview transcripts, personas, and common factors that represent typical experiences across the community, all of which were developed previous to the current reporting period. We distilled these materials into a small set of themes that were presented in a short paper published to the community.
- Gathering the insights gained in this analysis, as well as the material of the interviews, our earlier survey and associated analyses, and our experience in the community, we developed a visualization of typical career paths including various entry points, decisions and transitions, and possible career end-points or goals. The poster and an extended abstract of the work was submitted to and accepted for the Posters and Visualizations track of PEARC25, and will be presented there by Patrick Schmitz.

Much of this activity has been conducted in collaboration with the Staff and Student Workforce Development workstreams.

3 CaRCC Capabilities Model

The goal of the CaRCC Capabilities Model workstream is to develop a more robust and sustainable implementation of the CaRCC Capabilities Model assessment tool (renamed from the “RCD Capabilities Model” in response to community input) and an associated data-exploration portal that eliminates the need to create a host of individual reports by hand.

We originally had two broad objectives for the CaRCC Capabilities Model workstream:

- Implement a 2.0 version of the CaRCC Capabilities Model assessment tool and data exploration portal
- Expand consulting and support services to ensure a broad range of institutions can use the model and incorporate it into strategic planning work for their respective RCD programs

We built upon the 2.0 portal release (completed in the previous reporting period), adding several updates to the CaRCC Capabilities Model assessment tool and data portal, including new assessment tool options to support a broader range of needs and available resources, and additional tools for visualizing data and benchmarking reports.

In response to feedback from a number of smaller or under-resourced institutions and emerging RCD programs, the CaRCC Capabilities Model working group at CaRCC added a new **Essentials** assessment. This variant allows organizations to focus on 38 core capabilities, requiring a significantly reduced time commitment relative to a full assessment. This streamlined approach

makes the Capabilities Model more accessible to organizations with limited resources or those seeking a quick operational overview.

An additional variant addresses requests from community input to allow for more selective areas of assessment: The “Chart Your Own Journey” variant for assessments provides granular control and enables organizations to tailor their evaluations to specific strategic priorities, operational focus areas, or stakeholder requirements.

The data viewer was extended to provide individual capability-level graphing and comparisons, and benchmarking functionality was expanded to show capability-level benchmark reports, as well as to support the new assessment options.

The help documentation was revised and expanded to support all the new tools, and to better support new users exploring the tools. An accessibility review by the working group led to a number of changes in the user experience ranging from layout to fonts and colors.

We continue to see growth in adoption and use of the tools. There are now over 230 institutions using the tools, and these institutions represent all 50 states, two U.S. territories and the District of Columbia, five Canadian provinces, and several other countries outside North America. R1 universities dominate the mix, however just over half of institutions using the tools are from smaller universities, labs, and industry (see figure 1a). Of the 75 institutions that have completed and contributed assessments to the community dataset, nearly two-thirds are R1 Universities (as shown in figure 1b). It is worth noting that many institutions have completed

more than one assessment; there are now a total of 107 completed assessments in the community dataset. While all but two of these are full assessments, many of the recent contributions are Essentials assessments.

The community data set continues to provide insights into support for RCD across the community, and allows for comparisons to understand the differences among institutions within the community. For example, Figure 2 illustrates the stark differences between institutions in EPSCoR jurisdictions and those in non-EPSCoR jurisdictions related to support for Data Analysis.

Figure 2: A comparison of Data Analysis capabilities coverage by EPSCoR status (75 Institutions reporting).

We continue to update the tools to refine functionality and better support our users. We are also adding new reporting functionality and expanded role management capabilities to provide greater resilience in our data steward and related administrative roles.

Outreach and communications

We provide periodic reports and posts with analysis of the community dataset, although with the release of the data portal, users are no longer exclusively dependent upon these reports to explore and understand the data. We facilitate workshops and make presentations at ACM PEARC and other conferences (e.g., the CENVAL-ARC Conference (NSF Award 2346744)), and also conduct focus groups, etc. for working group activities.

Office hours

As part of support for the CaRCC Capabilities Model we have established regular office hours to provide support for institutions completing the Capabilities Model and for individuals needing more specific help. Discussions among individuals from participating institutions proved to be supportive and beneficial to both institutions and to the CaRCC Capabilities Model Working

Group with everything from approaches to campus participation to complete the survey, clarification on specific questions, and improvements for future versions of the Capabilities Model.

Office hours have been held monthly throughout the reporting period. Additional email follow-up addressed directly to working group members and to the capmodel-discuss@carcc.org mailing list have also resulted from office hours discussions.

Members of the CaRCC Capabilities Model working group have also met individually with representatives from institutions requesting specific attention to their questions about the Model and the submission process, as well as a discussion about strategies for engagement and best practices to complete the Model.

The CaRCC Capabilities Model Working Group will continue to host regular office hours, generally staffed by two to four working group members at each session. They will continue to be provided remotely via Zoom and regularly advertised to the CaRCC Capabilities Model participating institutions, general RCD community mailing lists, and the CaRCC and RCD Nexus websites and in relevant blog posts and newsletters.

4 RCD Staff Resources

RCD Nexus community development effort continues in the area of staff resources to support RCD professionals as well as to support institutions with RCD practitioners who support research activities. The key objectives are to address the challenges identified in a series of discussions, call for position papers and program experiences documentation, and hold a workshop.

These include:

- Identifying leading practices and common elements among staff workforce development programs.
- Propagating various models to support workforce development for staff RCD practitioners (as well as undergraduate and graduate students in collaboration with the RCD Nexus Student Workforce workstream effort.)
- Employing a “train the trainers” model to build a community of trainers that, in turn, helps educate other RCD professionals on workforce development topics.

The materials gathered will provide the basis for an analysis to identify gaps and needs for additional training programs that would facilitate the transition from other positions into RCD roles, and, for example, developing existing RCD staff into RCD leadership roles. We have found, in order to accomplish this, we first must foster the RCD community to understand these efforts.

Unlike some of the other work within the RCD Nexus, this effort is addressing newly identified needs, rather than continuing and growing efforts already underway.

Building a workforce development community

During the reporting period, we continued to grow a community of interested RCD professionals and provide opportunities for individuals to self-identify as participants in these workforce development efforts. In addition, we are seeing engagement by supervisors, managers, and directors who are shaping the RCD programs at institutions around the country and beyond.

RCD Nexus Day: In July 2024, at the RCD Nexus Day co-located with PEARC24, the Staff Workforce Development workshop held an all-day workshop with the topic of “What We’re Facing as Research Computing and Data (RCD) Professionals.” The goal was not only to be informative and spark discussion, but also to work towards deliverables that would be useful in the broader RCD community. The materials generated from the workshop were further refined and developed by the CaRCC Staff and Student Workforce Development Interest Group resulting in a paper describing a curated catalog of resources that can be used for training RCD Professionals titled “A Collaborative Catalog for Research Computing and Data Professional Development.” In addition to the catalog, the paper also discusses the need to develop a sustainable framework for curation and review. Additional details about the workshop can be found in the full RCD Nexus Day 2024 report.

- Elizabeth Hillery, Scott Delinger, James Leous, Lauren Michael, Timothy Middelkoop, David Reddy, Mary Ellen Sloane, and Michael D. Weiner. 2025. “A Collaborative Catalog for Research Computing and Data Professional Development.” In *Practice and Experience in Advanced Research Computing (PEARC '25)*, July 20--24, 2025, Columbus, OH, USA. ACM, New York, NY, USA 4 Pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3708035.3736050>

Staff Workforce Development Interest Group: This CaRCC interest group meets monthly with the Student Workforce Development Interest Group splitting call topics between staff and student focused roughly half the time and continues to gather and develop resources for RCD staff and student workforce development. The staff interest group has 94 members with diverse institutional representation led by Timothy Middelkoop and Michael Weiner (formerly Claire Mizumoto).

This year the bi-monthly calls have included content and discussions relevant to the creation of RCD training resources. Content from the community calls included:

- A discussion on current workforce development issues in the RCD community.
- A presentation and discussion on how to “maximize your conference experience” for RCD professionals attending conferences such as PEARC. The resulting discussion was published on the CaRCC website for future use.

<https://carcc.org/2024/07/17/workforce-development-maximizing-your-conference-experience/>

- A presentation and subsequent discussion of a paper presented at PEARC24 titled “Identifying learning pathways to guide the career development of technical professionals in research environments.”
- A discussion on “developing an RCD workforce resource catalog” to motivate the development of such a catalog.

The complete list of calls that include links to the video recordings of many of the sessions, presentation slides, and call documents can be found on the Staff and Student Workforce Development Interest Group web page at <https://carcc.org/staff-and-student-workforce-development/>. Many of the call docs contain rich information about the discussion during the call.

Additional activities developed from the Staff and Student Workforce Development effort include:

- CaRCC Mentoring working group was formed and is working to develop a mentoring program for RCD professionals. Because career development for such a new field is not supported by formal training, a specific degree or certified training, mentorship is critical to the growth and development of RCD professionals. During the past reporting year, the mentoring group developed a detailed RCD mentor program proposal and solicited partnerships with other organizations adjacent to CaRCC that have similar programs.
- Staff Workforce Development interest group standing committee on Gathering and Curating RCD Program Stories has been interviewing institutional representatives to tell the story of their RCD programs. These stories provide examples of programs, including their histories and successes. The complete list of interviews has been published and can be found at <https://carcc.org/2025/06/25/read-the-full-collection-of-carcc-rcd-program-stories/>

During the past reporting year the leadership of the staff and student workforce development interest groups have integrated further with the realization that the topics are strongly interrelated and plan to merge in the near future.

5 Student Workforce Development

The focus of the Student RCD Workforce Development aspect of the project is to explore existing models for student RCD workforce development at both the undergraduate and graduate levels. During this reporting period, we have made progress on moving forward our main goal to create a guide and other resources that share leading practices and models from

organizations who are already doing this successfully. This team works in close coordination with the staff workforce development efforts.

The RCD Student workforce development interest group continues to grow and develop under co-chairs (Hillery, Haymore, Cheatham, and formerly Orendt) in conjunction with the RCD Staff workforce development Interest group chairs. The group currently has 78 members. The interest group meets monthly with the Staff workforce development interest group with the calls split roughly between the two groups with some shared calls.

This year the bi-monthly calls have included content and discussions relevant to establishing and building RCD student programs and how to train, manage, and mentor students within the program. Content from the community calls included:

A presentation of the research computing student worker program at UVA, which covered the program's establishment, key milestones, progress to date, as well as the challenges faced as the initiative continues to grow and expand. The presentation was followed by a discussion.

- A discussion on how to effectively train student members of an RCD team.
- A discussion on how to effectively transition student workers into full-time roles within the RCD workforce.
- A discussion on how institutions structure their student workforce including best practices for assigning responsibilities, balancing workloads, and providing mentorship to maximize student contributions and career growth.

This year a number of calls have utilized a new call format that captures rich content from the participants in the call documents. The goal is to use this material for future resources. The call documents, videos, and slides can be found on the Staff and Student Workforce Development Interest Group web page at <https://carcc.org/staff-and-student-workforce-development/>.

6 Job Family Matrix Adoption

Much of the energy this year went into work in Section 7 - RCD Workforce Survey.

The dissemination efforts for RCD Job Family Matrix were ongoing, with 95 downloads during this reporting period. This brings the total number of downloads to 470 with 381 unique email addresses across more than 200 different institutions. We have identified additional institutions that are willing to be interviewed in their implementation efforts.

7 RCD Workforce Survey

Work in the last year by CaRCC's RCD Professionalization working group included finalizing a report on additional data analysis from the 2021 RCD Workforce Survey, and completing the development of the 2025 RCD Workforce Survey, later launched in July of 2025. With working group co-Chairs Ashley Stauffer (Penn State University) and Kimberly Grasch (U of Chicago) a number of other group members continuing (Chris Reidy, Levi Dolan, Ritika Giri), the group further expanded during the reporting period, with the addition of Kirk Anne (Rice University), Lauren Michael (prev LMichael Consulting / Internet2), Tim Servinsky (Penn State Harrisburg), and Nandan Tandon (University of Central Florida).

In December 2024, the group published the additional data analysis presented in last year's annual report, as a blog post on the CaRCC website (<https://carcc.org/2024/12/13/exploring-the-role-of-research-computing-and-data-rcd-professionals/>). In that report, a number of new questions were proposed for a future survey, which the group continued to work on, in parallel, for a repeat survey with both longitudinal research capability for previously-surveyed workforce characterizations, and additional survey content to address these and other new questions. Also with a goal of creating visualizations reflecting researcher-facing roles / facilitators, the group reviewed a number of articles and explored a wide range of options for creating visualizations and mapping activities of facilitators with an interest in making them interactive.

With the updated survey in IRB review as of the end of the reporting period (and deployed as of the writing of this report), it has been expanded to examine questions lie the following: How do measured characterizations change if more respondents understand and choose to identify their role with one or more of the RCD facings, or if with greater representation of non-R2 universities and minority-serving institutions, which were not well-represented in the first survey? To what extent might the RCD workforce identify as neurodivergent? Why did RCD professionals change employers? What general trends exist in these and other factors to potentially inform a trajectory of growth and change across the workforce?

As for the prior survey, the RCD Professionalization group will spearhead the data analysis and reporting on findings from the survey, including published papers, presentations to the community, reflections for a third survey, and opportunities for new community members to contribute to all of this work.

8 Program Administration

RCD Nexus consists of a set of related but distinct projects or workstreams, each managed by one of the Principal Investigators (PIs). The RCD Nexus team members also serve in various roles

across CaRCC including the Logistics and Engagement Operations groups, the People Network Strategy and Policy-facing track, in addition to the roles in these workstreams as co-chairs of the CaRCC Capabilities Model, RCD Professionalization, RCD Career Arcs, and RCD Staff and Student workforce groups. This year we also started a Membership and Financial Models group and a Communications and Outreach group.

In order to keep all these work areas in sync and to enable identification of cross-project risks and opportunities, we conducted a series of program administration activities during the reporting period, including:

- Coordinated the October 2024 CaRCC Annual meeting with participation from RCD Nexus and CaRCC Advisory Committees, CaRCC chairs, People Network Coordinators, and several individuals from adjacent RCD Communities. The report is available at <https://zenodo.org/records/14617850>.
- Facilitated the development of a model for a CaRCC Transitional Board. Coordinated the solicitation of nominations for the Transitional Board, oversaw the election process, and coordinated the initial meetings of the Transitional Board. See [section 11](#) for Transitional Board membership.
- Held the third annual RCD Nexus Day co-located with PEARC24. The report is available at <https://zenodo.org/records/13840204>.
- Lead and Contributed to CaRCC Chairs Monthly meetings.
- Contributed to CaRCC Logistics Operations group (Brunson is co-chair, Schmitz, Cheatham, and McCanse are members).
- Contributed to CaRCC Engagement Operations Group (Cheatham and McCanse are members).
- Led and contributed to the Membership and Financial Models group (McCanse is chair)
- Led and contributed to the Communications and Outreach Interest Group (McCanse is co-chair).
- Managed project and engagement planning activities which reflect plans and progress against milestones.
- Liaised with key collaborators and other community organization and project leads in order to establish and solidify partnerships (e.g., Brunson serves on external advisory boards for NSF ACCESS, NSF Jetstream2, NSF Chase-CI, Cloudbank, Nevada's NSF EPSCoR track 1 Harnessing the Data Revolution for Fire Science, etc)
- Managed sub-award contracts and oversaw spending
- Supported the continued use of program templates, policies, and procedures
- Posted presentations and other resources to the website and Zonodo for community use. (See section 10.)
- Disseminated program news and upcoming event information (see section 1)

9 Looking Forward

The RCD Nexus grant has laid a solid foundation for the sustained growth and impact of CaRCC and the broader RCD community. The extensive volunteer network that drives CaRCC's work—including all committees and working groups established and strengthened through RCD Nexus support—will continue their vital contributions to the RCD profession. The infrastructure and central coordination mechanisms developed during the grant period have proven essential and will remain active as CaRCC moves forward.

Most significantly, the strategic planning activities, workshops, and community engagement efforts supported by the RCD Nexus grant have directly informed CaRCC's decision to pursue 501(c)(3) nonprofit status. This pivotal step, which emerged from extensive community consultation and strategic retreats funded by the grant, will provide the organizational stability and independence necessary to sustain and expand CaRCC's mission. Alongside this transition, CaRCC is developing a comprehensive membership model and sustainability plan—initiatives that grew directly from the needs assessment and strategic planning exercises conducted throughout the grant period.

The priorities identified during the RCD Nexus grant—including the refinement of the Capabilities Model tools and coordination of professional development resources—will all continue as core CaRCC initiatives. One of the main priorities – expansion of the Career Arcs research – was completed and the results published, however this work will continue to inform related activities including RCD Professionalization. As CaRCC moves forward with its 501(c)(3) application and membership model implementation, the organization is well-positioned to address the growing demand for RCD professional support services identified during the grant period. The consulting, training, and communication capabilities developed through RCD Nexus funding will evolve into sustainable service offerings that can support both the RCD community and the organization's long-term viability.

The RCD Nexus grant has been instrumental in transforming CaRCC from a grassroots volunteer effort into a maturing organization capable of serving as the professional home for RCD practitioners nationwide. The strategic decisions and organizational developments that emerged from this support ensure that the impact of the RCD Nexus investment will continue to grow, ultimately achieving the long-term vision of establishing a fully resourced professional society that advances both RCD professionals and the research enterprise they enable.

10 Publications and Presentations

Publications

- Elizabeth Hillery, Scott Delinger, James Leous, Lauren Michael, Timothy Middelkoop, David Reddy, Mary Ellen Sloane, and Michael D. Weiner. 2025. [A Collaborative Catalog for Research Computing and Data Professional Development](https://doi.org/10.1145/3708035.3736050). In Practice and Experience in Advanced Research Computing 2025: The Power of Collaboration (PEARC '25). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, Article 79, 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3708035.3736050>
- Alber, A., Briggs, L., Brunk, P., Joshi, M., Kamble, A., Kefi, A., Middelkoop, T., Sarajlic, S., Sokovic, A., Valdez, J., and Zhang, Y. 2025. [AI Project Facilitation Guidance for Research Computing and Data \(RCD\) Professionals](https://doi.org/10.1145/3708035.3736061). In Practice and Experience in Advanced Research Computing 2025: The Power of Collaboration (PEARC '25). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, Article 70, 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3708035.3736061>
- Andino, G., Delinger, S., Tande, J.F., Middelkoop, T., Mizumoto, C., Reddy, D., and Weiner, M. 2024. [Onboarding Research Computing and Data Professionals](https://doi.org/10.1145/3626203.3670582). Practice and Experience in Advanced Research Computing (PEARC '24), Providence, RI. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3626203.3670582>
- Brunson, D., Hicks, J., Hillery, E. A., Siefert McCause, D., Michael, L., Middelkoop, T., & Schmitz, P. (2024). [RCD Nexus Day 2024 Final Report](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13840204). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13840204>
- Campus Research Computing Consortium (CaRCC). (2025). [CaRCC 2024 Annual Retreat Report](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14617850). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14617850>
- Freeman Jr, R. M., Anne, K. M., Smith, G. K., Yin, W., Speyer, G., & Reidy, C. (2024, April 26). [Membership and Participation in our RCD Communities: What is it and how are we doing?](https://doi.org/10.1145/3626203.3670630). Practice and Experience in Advanced Research Computing (PEARC '24), Providence, RI. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3626203.3670630>
- Giri, R., Yockel, S., Grash, K., Stauffer, A., Robila, S., & Reidy, C. (2025). [Examining RCD Roles and Activities through the Lens of Facings](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15059460). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15059460>
- Hicks, J., Brunson, D., Chadalapaka, S., Ghahramani, F., Michael, L., and Weilhamer, C. 2024. [Kickstarting Research Support at Under-Resourced Institutions: A Starter Guide to Advance Your Self-Assessment of Research Computing and Data Capabilities](https://doi.org/10.1145/3626203.3670572). In Practice and Experience in Advanced Research Computing 2024: Human Powered Computing (PEARC '24). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, Article 85, 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3626203.3670572>
- Hillery, E., Delinger, S., Leous, J., Michael, L., Middelkoop, T., Reddy, D., Sloane, M.E., and Weiner, M. 2025. [A Collaborative Catalog for Research Computing and Data Professional Development](https://doi.org/10.1145/3708035.3736050). In Practice and Experience in Advanced Research Computing 2025: The Power of Collaboration (PEARC '25). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, Article 79, 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3708035.3736050>

- Schmitz, P., Porter, S., McCaffrey, D., Humphreys, M., & Kee, K. (2025). Career Arcs Phase 2 Interview script. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15053054>
- Schmitz, P., & Porter, S. (2025). A Visualization of Patterns and Themes in RCD Professional Career Paths. In Practice and Experience in Advanced Research Computing (PEARC '25), Columbus, OH, USA. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3708035.3736028>
- Schmitz, P., & Porter, S. (2025). A Visualization of Patterns and Themes in RCD Professional Career Paths (Poster Image). Practice and Experience in Advanced Research Computing (PEARC25), Columbus, Ohio. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15048236>

Presentations (listed chronologically)

- CaRCC Parade (January, virtual, CaRCC People Network)
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ITQG7SUwm-E>
https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1TYnqxWc-MTfaDGmf3A7B7cJycNzDMPdYJnfOISHCBTI/edit?slide=id.g26677f299bf_20_0, January 28, 2025.
- CaRCC Town Hall 2024
Panel: Daphne McCanse, Dana Brunson, Tom Cheatham, Patrick Schmitz, Scott Yockel, Bob Freeman and Lauren Michael.
<https://carcc.org/2024/07/09/carcc-at-pearc24-headed-to-providence-heres-your-guide-to-all-things-carcc/>
<https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1jHHNY3orGoFKIdHL3sflw0sqkN7K5IXvHwltbcblkkg>
- CaRCC People Network – Emerging Centers Track BoF at PEARC24, Jane Combs, Richard Knepper, Patrick Clemens
https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1CZevO6-TVmvf3fliIgfIC8sWRZPSvCYxNk_VRv6Nvk/
- An overview of the CaRCC Capabilities Model Assessment Tools and Data Viewer, Presentation to Joint CaRCC/CASC meeting Tuesday, October 15th, 2024, Patrick Schmitz
<https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/17t4yZ3Nit7tVrfVrvEMawgvhmXHI8jpnFqSP0kOs8gU/>
- An overview of the CaRCC Capabilities Model and the new Assessment Tools, Presentation to ILight Town Hall, Tuesday, January 28th, 2025, John Hicks
<https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1pWSPWsxYDaigZ-1DYg3wpuZ9pyTBXVV-1vw3v7hgjZs/>
- CaRCC: Supporting Excellence in Research Computing and Data (RCD) and an Introduction to CI planning tools, CENVAL-ARC Symposium 2025, March 6, 2025, Patrick Schmitz,
<https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1ulsDSlJ8teBiVaOTSxJa8XhBl44jGuzngAJou3xNuV4/>
- BoF: Amplifying RCD Impact Through Strategic Communications and Outreach, Eric Adams, Daphne McCanse.
https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1t9Me0BK9Aqsz-ahRshxsZ4_O_bBUh46bliZD0ufiaTk/

Workshops

- CaRCC Annual Strategic retreat in June 2024, report available <https://zenodo.org/records/14617850>
- RCD Nexus Day co-located event (<https://carcc.org/2024/04/24/2024-rcd-nexus-day-register-now/>) prior to PEARC24 with two workshops: *What We're Facing as RCD Professionals* and *Data Governance and Working with Data*. Sunday, July 21st, 2024
- Building and selling a strategic plan for your Research Computing and Data program, PEARC25 Workshop

Events

- Internet2 hosted a “Coffee with CaRCC” for research computing and data professionals who are part of the Campus Research Computing Consortium (CaRCC) on Wednesday November 20 from 10-11 a.m. at SC24, and again Tuesday July 23rd 10:30-11:30 a.m. at PEARC24. <https://internet2.edu/sc24-arrives-in-atlanta-this-november-see-what-internet2-has-in-store/>
- Internet2 provided information about CaRCC, RCD Nexus, MS-CC and other community organizations along with literature and stickers at their sponsor booth at PEARC24 and at PEARC25. <https://internet2.edu/2024-rcd-nexus-day-register-now/>, <https://internet2.edu/internet2-plays-key-roles-in-pearc25-conference/>

Media

- Community Exchange 2024 blog; <https://internet2.edu/countdown-to-2024-internet2-community-exchange-part2/>

People Network sessions - Recordings available on YouTube ([link](#)).

Plenaries:

- Requesting Resources via the National AI Research Resource Pilot (twice)
- 2025-01-28 Annual CaRCC Parade

Data Facing Track (First Tuesdays):

- Research Data Access and Preservation Conference Recap (4/1/2025)
- High Performance Computing 101 (3/4/2025)
- Realities of Academic Data Sharing (RADS) Initiative (2/4/2025)
- Reflect on past year's session / Look forward to new year's session (1/7/2025)
- NIST Research Data Framework (11/5/2024)
- Joint Data-Facing & Systems-Facing Call: NSPM-33 – Not a Type of Sun Lotion (10/1/2024)
- The Intersection of AI and Cybersecurity (9/3/2024)

- PEARC24 Community Report (8/6/2024)
- Unconference with Breakouts on Generated Topics (6/4/2024)
- Beyond the Business Case: Universally Designing the Workplace for Neurodiversity and Inclusion (5/7/2024)

Emerging Centers Track (Third Wednesdays):

- RCD Origin Stories #1 (4/16/2025)
- Affinity Group Community Discussion (3/19/2025)
- Research Computing at Smaller Institutions (RCSI) Overview (2/19/2025)
- Generative AI Use in the Research Enterprise (1/15/2025)
- In-Person Social at SC24 in Atlanta, GA (11/20/2024)
- Cybersecurity Month: An Overview of Cybersecurity Resources for Emerging Centers (10/23/2024)
- Responding to the Emerging Centers PEARC24 BoF (9/18/2024)
- PEARC24 Recap and Emerging Centers BoF Debrief (8/21/2024)
- The National Artificial Intelligence Research Resource (NAIRR) Pilot (6/26/2024)
- Open Science Grid (OSG) for Emerging Centers (5/15/2024)

Researcher-Facing Track (Second Thursdays):

- AlphaFold – what it is and how to support it (2/13/2025)
- Planning for the new year! 2025 call topic (1/9/2025)
- Research Process Automation with Globus (11/14/2024)
- Ask Your Researcher-Facing Peers: What Are You Doing About Cybersecurity? (10/10/2024)
- Spack: A package manager for supercomputers (9/12/2024)
- PEARC '24 Recap (8/15/2024)
- ACCESS Pegasus – A hosted workflow system for ACCESS users (6/13/2024)
- Open On Demand: Improvements and Recent developments (5/9/2024)

Strategy and Policy-Facing Track (First Wednesdays):

- Planning for Resilience (5/7/2025)
- CASC, RDAP, ABRF, and NAIRR Pilot recap (4/2/2025)
- The data problem (3/5/2025)
- Round robin discussion and 2025 preview (2/5/2025)
- RCD Workforce Interest Group Call (12/3/2024)
- Meetings recap: CaRCC Retreat, Fall CASC Meeting, EDUCAUSE (11/6/2024)
- RCD Cybersecurity Requirements, Trends, and Use-Cases Across Different Institution Types (10/2/2024)
- Reflections and discussion of PEARC24 (8/7/2024)
- Leadership Training Programs (6/5/2024)
- Panel: Institutional Metadata (5/1/2024)

Systems-Facing Track (Third Thursdays):

- Accessibility Tools for Linux System Administrators (5/15/2025)
- Software Installation Strategies Panel (4/17/2025)
- NodeMan, a Node Management tool for HPC (3/20/2025)
- Openstack Operators Discuss Life With Openstack (2/20/2025)
- Container Adoption in Campus High Performance Computing (1/16/2025)
- NSPM-33 – Not a Type of Sun Lotion (10/1/2024)
- On-Premises Storage Solutions and Growth Projection in Research Computing (9/19/2024)
- PEARC '24 Recap – Combined call with Researcher-Facing Track (8/15/2024)
- Debian GNU/Linux for Scientific Research (6/20/2024)

In our monthly call announcement, CaRCC provides information on additional community opportunities including the US Research Software Engineers and EDUCAUSE RCD Community Group monthly community calls, the OSG Consortium and NSF PATH weekly Office Hours, and the Regulated Research Community of Practice Community Discussions.

11 CaRCC Transitional Board

In February, 2025 CaRCC Chairs and Steering Committee Members voted to elect a CaRCC Transitional Board as an important first step toward a long-term goal of becoming a 501(c)(3) nonprofit organization. The Transitional Board will be responsible for conducting the legal and financial transactions of CaRCC, maintaining CaRCC bylaws, and conducting the administrative tasks associated with obtaining nonprofit status and partnerships.

Officers

Dana Brunson, Internet2 — Board Chair

Lauren Michael, LMichael Consulting / Internet2 — Board Vice-Chair

Daphne McCanse, Daphne McCanse Consulting / Internet2 — Board Secretary

Members

Thomas Cheatham, University of Utah

Bob Freeman, Harvard University

Amy Koshoffer, University of Cincinnati

Jason Simms, Swarthmore College

Patrick Schmitz, Semper Cogito Consulting

James Wilgenbusch, University of Minnesota

12 Committees and Working Groups

CaRCC Advisory Committee

Jim Bottum (co-chair)

Jackie Milhans, Northwestern (co-chair)

Linda Akli, Texas Advanced Computing Center/University of Texas, Austin

Danielle Cooper, Ithaka S+R

Ana Hunsinger, Internet2

Ann Kovalchick, University of California, Merced

Erik Lundberg, University of Washington

Susan Mehringer, Cornell University

Henry Neeman, University of Oklahoma

Amy Neeser, University of California, Berkeley

Dan Stanzione, Texas Advanced Computing Center/University of Texas, Austin

Ashley Stauffer, Penn State University

CaRCC Chairs Leadership

Eric Adams, Purdue University, (RCD Communications and Outreach)

Amit Amritkar, Penn State University (Strategy & Policy-Facing Track)

Venice Bayrd, Montana State (EPSCoR Cyberinfrastructure)

Justin Booth, Michigan State University (Researcher-Facing Track)

Dana Brunson, Internet2 (Logistics; NSF CaRCC NAIRR EAGER PI)

Cyd Burrows-Schilling, UC San Diego (Research Cybersecurity)

Thomas Cheatham, University of Utah (RCD Student Workforce Development)

Jason Christopher, UC Berkeley (HIPAA Challenges)

Patrick Clemens, University of Vermont (Emerging Centers Track)

Sean Cleveland, The University of Hawaii System (EPSCoR Cyberinfrastructure)

Will Drake, Indiana University (Research Cybersecurity)

Bob Freeman, Harvard Business School (retired) (People Network)

Kimberly Grasch, University of Chicago (RCD Professionalization)

Brian Haymore, University of Utah (RCD Student Workforce Development; Systems-Facing Track)

Betsy Hillery, Purdue University (RCD Student Workforce Development, Workforce Mentoring)

Daniel Howard, UCAR (AI Facilitation)

Manasvita Joshi, Harvard University (Anaconda Transition)

Neill Killgore, Louisiana State University (AI Facilitation)

Alper Kinaci, Northwestern University (Workforce Mentoring)

Richard Knepper, Cornell University (Emerging Centers Track)

Amy Koshoffer, University of Cincinnati (Data-Facing Track)

Geoffrey Lentner, Purdue University (Anaconda Transition)

Julie Ma, Massachusetts Green High Performance Computing Center (Engagement)

Deb McCaffrey, Arizona State University (HIPAA Challenges; Data-Facing Track)
Daphne McCanse (RCD Communications and Outreach; NSF CaRCC NAIRR EAGER co-PI)
Lauren Michael, LMichael Consulting / Internet2 contract (Logistics; People Network; AI Facilitation Materials; CaRCC Capabilities Model; NSF CaRCC NAIRR EAGER co-PI)
Timothy Middelkoop, Internet2 (RCD Staff Workforce Development; AI Facilitation Materials; NSF CaRCC NAIRR EAGER PI)
Sam Porter, University of Maryland (Career Arcs)
Chris Reidy, University of Arizona (Engagement)
Patrick Schmitz, Semper Cogito Consulting (CaRCC Capabilities Model; Career Arcs)
Jason Simms, Swarthmore (Emerging Centers Track)
Matthew Smith, University British Columbia (Systems-Facing Track)
Scotty Strachan, Nevada System of Higher Education (EPSCoR Cyberinfrastructure)
Ashley Stauffer, Penn State University (RCD Professionalization)
Jeffrey Weekley, UC Santa Cruz (Research Cybersecurity)
Michael Weiner, Georgia Institute of Technology (RCD Staff Workforce Development)

AI Facilitation Interest Group

Group website: <https://carcc.org/ai-facilitation-ig/>

Daniel Howard (co-Chair), University Corporation for Atmospheric Research (NSF NCAR / UCAR)
Semir Sarajlic (co-Chair), Vanderbilt University
Forough Ghahramani (co-Chair), NJEdge Inc.

AI Facilitation Materials Working Group

Group website: <https://carcc.org/ai-facilitation-materials-working-group/>

Lauren Michael (co-Chair), LMichael Consulting / Internet2 (contract)
Timothy Middelkoop (co-Chair), Internet2
Amira Kefi, University of Illinois
Anna Alber, Chapman University
Atish Kamble, Boston University
Don Richards, Johns Hopkins University
Jeffrey N. Valdez, Georgia Institute of Technology
Laura Briggs, Information Consultant, Wheatley, ON
Manasvita Joshi, Harvard University
Paul Brunk, University of Georgia
Semir Sarajlic, Vanderbilt University
Ying Zhang, University of Florida

Anaconda Transition Working Group

Group website: <https://carcc.org/anaconda-transition-working-group/>

Geoffrey Lentner (co-Chair), Purdue University
Manasvita Joshi (co-Chair)
Aldo Romero, West Virginia University

Anna Alber, Chapman University
Bryan Raney, Rice University
Ian Kaufman, University of California San Diego
Joseph Creech, the George Washington University
Lev Gorenstein, Globus / University of Chicago
William Warriner, University of Alabama at Birmingham

Capabilities Model Working Group

Group website: <https://carcc.org/rcdcm/>
Patrick Schmitz (co-Chair), Semper Cogito
Lauren Michael (co-Chair), LMichael Consulting / Internet2
Dana Brunson, Internet2
Paul Fischer, University of Utah
Forough Ghahramani, NJEdge
John Hicks, Internet2
Caroline Welhamer, Indiana University

Communications and Outreach Interest Group

Daphne McCanse, CaRCC (co-chair)
Eric Adams, Purdue University (co-chair)

EPSCoR CI Council Interest Group

Group website: <https://carcc.org/epscor-ci/>
This group emerged from the previous EPSCoR CI Working group which produced a report [“Minding the Gap: Leveraging Cyberinfrastructure to Transform EPSCoR Jurisdictions”](#)

Chairs:

Venice Bayrd, Montana State (co-Chair)
Sean Cleveland, University of Hawai'i System (co-Chair)
Scotty Strachan, Nevada System of Higher Education (co-Chair)

Steering Committee (in addition to the co-chairs):

Gwen Jacobs (U Hawaii)
Fred Harris (UN Reno)
Dana Brunson (Internet2)
Patrick Schmitz (Semper Cogito)

CI Council members:

Liam Forbes, University of Alaska
Vincent Dela Cruz, University of Guam
Sean Cleveland, University of Hawaii
Luke Sheneman, University of Idaho
Sarah Diesburg, University of Iowa
Anthony Elam, University of Kentucky
Kevin Wentworth, University of Maine

Michael Navicky, University of Mississippi
Venice Bayrd, University of Montana
Scotty Strachan, University of Nevada
Isis Serna, University of New Mexico
Henry Neeman, University of Oklahoma
Ashley Podhradsky, Dakota State University
Brent Van Aartsen, Dakota State University
Patrick Clemins, University of Vermont
Kelly Harrigan, University of Virgin Islands
Jeffrey Hamerlinck, University of Wyoming

HIPAA Challenges Interest Group

Website: <https://carcc.org/hipaa-challenges/>

Deb McCaffrey, Arizona State University (co-chair)
Jason Christopher, University of California, Berkeley (co-chair)
Ian Brooks, CU Anschutz
Jil Gemmill, Clemson University
Jim Kenyon, University of Michigan
Tobin Magle, Northwestern
Andrea McColl, UCLA
Timothy Stark, CU Anschutz
Mike Warfe, Case Western

Mentoring working group

Betsy Hillary, Purdue University (co-chair)
Alper Kinaci, Northwestern University (co-chair)
Claire Mizumoto, University of California, San Diego
Xinlei Qiu, member (Stanford University)
Brad Spitzbart, member (Harvard University)
Jim Leous, member (Pennsylvania State University)

RCD Career Arcs Working Group *(work completed)*

Group Website: <https://carcc.org/career-arcs/>

Patrick Schmitz, University of Maryland (co-chair)
Sam Porter, Semper Cogito Consulting (co-chair)

RCD Professionalization Working Group

Group website: <https://carcc.org/rcd-professionalization/>

Ashley Stauffer (co-Chair), Penn State University
Kimberly Grasch (co-Chair), University of Chicago
Chris Reidy, University of Arizona
Kirk Anne, Rice University

Lauren Michael, LMichael Consulting / Internet2 (contract)
Levi Dolan, Yale University
Nandan Tandon, University of Central Florida
Tim Servinsky, Penn State Harrisburg

Research Cybersecurity Interest Group

Jeffrey Weekley (co-chair), UC Santa Cruz
Will Drake (co-chair), Indiana University
Cyd Burrows-Schilling (co-chair), UC San Diego

RCD Staff Workforce Development Interest Group

Group website: <https://carcc.org/staff-and-student-workforce-development/>

Timothy Middelkoop, Internet2 (co-chair)
Michael Weiner, Georgia Institute of Technology (co-chair)
Gladys Andino, University of Virginia
Janae Baker, Rutgers University
Joshua Baller, University of Minnesota
Caughlin Bohn, University of Nebraska
Dana Brunson, Internet2
Katia Bulekova, Boston University
Tom Cheatham, University of Utah
Michael Colee, UC Santa Barbara
Jonathan Cranford, NC State University
Scott Delinger, University of Alberta
Jonathan Dursi, Research Computing Teams
Tony Elam, University of Kentucky
Nathan Elger, USC
Grace Faustino, University of New Mexico
Mego Franks, Wake Forest School of Medicine
Layla Freeborn, University of Colorado-Boulder
Bob Freeman, Harvard Business School
Jeff Gardner, University of British Columbia
Jill Gemmill, Clemson
Forough Ghahramani, NJEdge
Toolika Ghose, University of Nebraska
Toolika Ghose, University of Nebraska System
Tom Gulbransen, NSF
Scott Hampton, Notre Dame
Chuntida Harinnitisuk, University of Texas Health Science Center at San Antonio
Amanda Hassenplug, Purdue
Brian Haymore, University of Utah

Betsy Hillery, Purdue University
Susan Ivey, NC State
Jessica Johnson, MS-CC (Internet2)
Matthew Keeler, University of Missouri System
Kathryn Kelley, CASC
Alper Kinaci, Northwestern University
Matt Lacy, Texas A&M
AJ Lauer, NCAR
Kristin Lepping, Rutgers University
Shuai Liu, University of arkansas
Chris Loken, Compute Ontario
Erik Lundberg, University of Washington
Jose Martinez, UCLA
Deb McCaffrey, Arizona State University
Daphne McCause, CaRCC
Maggie McFee, Harvard
Randy Melen, Stanford University
Benjamin Meyers, Rochester Institute of Technology
Timothy Middelkoop, Internet2
Jackie Milhans, Northwestern University
Claire Mizumoto, UCSD
Julia Mullen, MIT
Mary Murphy, University of Wisconsin-Madison
Pradeep Nagaraj, Bath
Henry Neeman, University of Oklahoma-Norman
Amy Neeser, Berkeley
Alastair Neil, George Mason University
Janna Nugent, Northwestern University
Amy Nurnberger, Massachusetts Institute of Technology
Colin Odden, The Ohio State University
Sarah Oelker, Oelker Data Services
Anita Orendt, University of Utah
Arman Pazouki, Purdue
Dylan Perkins, CU- Boulder
Laura Pettit, Indiana University
Roy Prouty, UMBC
Joe Rasche, Texas A&M University San Antonio
Mike Renfro, Tennessee Technological University
Nick Rochlin, University of British Columbia
Alyza Rosario, University of British Columbia
Jayshree Sarma, George Mason University

Patrick Schmitz, Semper Cogito
Sandy Shew, The Ohio State University
Breanna Shi, Georgia Institute of Technology
Swabir Silayi, George Mason University
Christopher Simmons, Massachusetts Institute of Technology
Winona Snapp-Childs, Indiana University
Ashley Stauffer, Penn State
Sheri Stebenne, Texas A&M University
Michael Stoppay, Montclair State University
Scotty Strachan, NV System of Higher Education, NevadaNet
Georgia Stuart, UMass Amherst
Richard Swilley, University of Florida
Berhane Temelso, George Mason University
Mandy Terrill, Oregon Health & Science University
Laura Theademan, Purdue University
Kimberly Thomas, UC San Diego
Olamide Timothy Tawose, Lincoln University of Pennsylvania
Nur Goldner Cohen Tzedek, UC Berkeley
Ravi Vadapalli, University of Miami
Kevin Van Slyke, SUNY University at Buffalo
Qinghua Wang, University of Delaware
Amanda Warren-Glowe, Purdue University
Michael Weiner, Georgia Tech
Nicole Winkler, Wayne State University
Feng Zhang, Stonybrook
Biru Zhou, McGill University

RCD Student Workforce Development Interest Group

Group website: <https://carcc.org/staff-and-student-workforce-development/>

Thomas Cheatham, University of Utah (co-chair)
Betsy Hillery, Purdue University (co-chair)
Brian Haymore, University of Utah (co-chair)
Gladys Andino, University of Virginia
Janae Baker, Rutgers University
Venice Bayrd, Montana State University
Rebecca Belshe, Arizona State University
John Bradley, Mississippi State University
John Bradley, Mississippi State University
Dana Brunson, Internet2
Katia Bulekova, Boston University
Dhruva Chakravorty, Texas A&M

Dhruv Chakravorty, Texas A&M
Thomas Cheatham, University of Utah
Michael Colee, UC Santa Barbara
Scott Coughlin, Northwestern
Jonathan Cranford, NC State University
Virginia Do, NCAR
Matthew Dorsey, North Carolina State University
Jonathan Dursi, Research Computing Teams
Nathan Elger, USC
Pedram Esfahani, The University of Chicago
Pedram Esfahani, The University of Chicago
Jacob Fosso Tande, NC State University (formerly UNC Greensboro)
Nikki Galloway, Old Dominion University
Jill Gemmill, Clemson
Forough Ghahramani, NJEdge
Tom Gulbransen, NSF
Amanda Hassenplug, Purdue University
Amanda Hassenplug, Purdue
Brian Haymore, University of Utah
Betsy Hillery, Purdue University
Jessica Johnson, MS-CC (Internet2)
Kathryn Kelley, CASC
Alper Kinaci, Northwestern University
Elizabeth Kinney, UBC
Matt Lacy, Texas A&M University
AJ Lauer, NCAR
Shuai Liu, University of Arkansas
Erik Lundberg, University of Washington
Jose Martinez, UCLA
Deb McCaffrey, Arizona State University
Daphne McCanse, CaRCC
Benjamin Meyers, Rochester Institute of Technology
Timothy Middelkoop, Internet2
Claire Mizumoto, UCSD
Mary Murphy, University of Wisconsin-Madison
Pradeep Nagaraj, Bath
Ryan Nakashima, SDSC/UCSD
Henry Neeman, University of Oklahoma-Norman
Amy Neeser, Berkeley
Jenny Nguyen, SDSC/UCSD
Amy Numberger, Massachusetts Institute of Technology

Anita Orendt, University of Utah
Daria Orłowska, Western Michigan University
Marinus Pennings, Texas A&M
Dylan Perkins, CU- Boulder
Laura Pettit, Indiana University
Craig Pohl, Washington University in St Louis
Roy Prouty, UMBC
David Reddy, University of South Carolina
Chris Reidy, University of Arizona
Mike Renfro, Tennessee Technological University
Carolina Roe-Raymond, Princeton
Alyza Rosario, University of British Columbia
Rahul Salla, Arizona State University
Paula Sanematsu, FAS-RC Harvard University
Jayshree Sarma, George Mason University
Patrick Schmitz, Semper Cogito
Andrew Sherman, Yale
Swabir Silayi, George Mason University
Karsten Siller, University of Virginia
Mary Sloane, Middle Tennessee State University
Sheri Stebenne, Texas A&M University
Michael Stoppay, Montclair State University
Scotty Strachan, NV System of Higher Education, NevadaNet
Georgia Stuart, UMass Amherst
Berhane Temelso, George Mason University
Laura Theademan, Purdue University
Chuck Thompson, Yale
Nur Goldner Cohen Tzedek, UC Berkeley
Ravi Vadapalli, University of Miami
Kevin Van Slyke, SUNY University at Buffalo
Tanvi Verma, University of Pittsburgh
Shu Wan, University at Buffalo
Amanda Warren-Glowe, Purdue University
Michael Weiner, Georgia Tech
Biru Zhou, McGill University

People Network <https://carcc.org/people-network/>

Bob Freeman, Harvard Business School (co-chair)

Lauren Michael, LMichael Consulting / Internet2 contract (co-chair)

Researcher-Facing Track <https://carcc.org/people-network/researcher-facing-track/>

Justin Booth, Michigan State University (co-coordinator)

Steering Committee:

Gladys Karina Andino Bautista

Katia Bulekova

Tobin Magle

Martin Cuma

Systems-Facing Track <https://carcc.org/people-network/systems-facing-track/>

Brian Haymore, University of Utah (co-coordinator)

Matthew Smith, Columbia University (co-coordinator)

Steering Committee:

John Blaas, Lambda

Nick Eggleston, Federal Reserve Bank of Kansas City

Jim Leous, Penn State

Ben Nickell, Idaho National Laboratory

Dori Sajdak, University at Buffalo

Nathan Wells, Kansas State University

Data-Facing Track <https://carcc.org/people-network/data-facing-track/>

Amy Koshoffer, University of Cincinnati (co-coordinator)

Deb McCaffrey, Arizona State University (co-coordinator)

Steering Committee:

Moira Downey

Lauren Michael

Cameron Cook

Zoe Braiterman

Strategy & Policy-Facing Track

<https://carcc.org/people-network/strategy-and-policy-facing-track/>

Amit Amritkar, Penn State, (co-coordinator)

Chuck Pavloski, University of Illinois (co-coordinator)

Steering Committee:

Patrick Schmitz, Semper Cogito

Jackie Milhans, Northwestern

Jason Simms, Swarthmore

Jim Wilgenbusch, Minnesota
Melissa Cragin, Rice University
Preston Smith, Purdue
Rich Knepper, Cornell
Susan Ivey, North Carolina State University
Thomas Cheatham, Utah
Pamela Reynolds, UC Davis
Michael Navicky, Mississippi State University

Emerging Centers Track <https://carcc.org/people-network/emerging-centers-track/>

Jason Simms, Swarthmore College (co-coordinator)
Patrick Clemens, University of Vermont (co-coordinator)

Steering Committee:

Andy Anderson, Amherst College
Kirk Anne, Rice University
Michael Benedetto, American Museum of Natural History
Jane Combs, University of Cincinnati
Forough Ghahramani, NJEdge, Inc.
Kinji Leslie, University of California, Santa Barbara
Rich Knepper, Cornell University
Shane Moeykens, University of Maine
Mike Renfro, Tennessee Technological University
Bobby Royba, University of Nevada, Las Vegas
Preston Smith, Purdue University

Operations and Infrastructure Groups

Engagement Operations Group

Julie Ma, Massachusetts Green High Performance Computing Center (co-chair)
Chris Reidy, University of Arizona (co-chair)
Cyd Burrows-Schilling, University of California San Diego
Tom Cheatham, University of Utah
Bob Freeman, Harvard Business School
Tracy Smith, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign

Logistics

Dana Brunson, Internet2 (co-chair)
Lauren Michael, LMichael Consulting / Internet2 (contract) (co-chair)
Thomas Cheatham, University of Utah
Bob Freeman, Harvard Business School
Timothy Middelkoop, Internet2

Patrick Schmitz, Semper Cogito Consulting
Daphne McCause, CaRCC

Membership and Financial Models Group

Daphne McCause, CaRCC (co-chair)
Ashley Stauffer, Penn State (co-chair)
Dana Brunson, Internet2
Bob Freeman, Harvard University
Kathryn Kelley, Coalition for Academic Scientific Computation (CASC)
Deb McCaffrey, Arizona State University
Lauren Michael, LMichael Consulting / Internet2 (contract)
Patrick Schmitz, Semper Cogito Consulting

Metrics Committee

Bob Freeman, Harvard Business School (chair)
Kirk Anne, Rice University
Kerk Kee, University of Texas, Austin
Timothy Middelkoop, Internet2
Patrick Schmitz, Semper Cogito Consulting
Gabriel Smith, Cornell University
Sarah Woolverton, Harvard Business School

Web Committee

Cyd Burrows-Schilling, University of California San Diego
Sean Cleveland, University of Hawaii System
Bob Freeman, Harvard Business School
Daphne McCause, CaRCC
Patrick Schmitz, Semper Cogito Consulting